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Multifunctional Composites with Modified Carbon Fibers for Lightning Strike Protection

Anchalee Duongthipthewa and Limin Zhou*

Department of Mechanical Engineering, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong

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Objectives

- To enhance mechanical and functional properties
- To provide adequate capability due to lightning strikes
- To ascertain the damage behavior of CFRP laminates with/without lightning strike protection (LSP) system using numerical models.

Lightning strike effect

Composite Content by Weight

B787

A350

- 1-2 times a year (1,000 to 10,000 hours of flight)
- ### Direct Damages

- Local burnt and fracture of structures
 - Extremely high voltage spark propagation
 - local heat generation

Indirect Damages

- Interference in the electronic systems
 - High electromagnetic field disorder

LSP system

Aircraft's outer skin → metallic structures → Good thermal and electrical conductivities in outer shell to provides a path for the electric current

~~Bonding Aluminum or Copper foil/mesh as the outside ply or embedded one ply down~~

Risk of galvanic corrosion
Weight increase

CFRP require to develop an alternative carbon based conducting composites, enabling the removal of metals

CONDUCTIVITY OF METALS COMPARED

CONDUCTIVITY / UNIT WEIGHT

Thermal Conductivity of Aluminium Compared with other Metals

per UNIT WEIGHT

Methods

Numerical Model

COMSOL

A coupled thermal-electrical model
Woven CFRP composites (T300B) with 16-ply
Atmospheric Temperature = 25°C
Thermal radiation, Emissivity (ϵ) = 0.9

Top Surface
Thermal radiation

Bottom Surface
Adiabatic

Side Surface
Electrical Potential ($E = 0V$)
Thermal radiation

Numerical Model

$$\text{Decomposition Index (DI)} = \begin{cases} 0 & T < 300^\circ\text{C} \\ \frac{T - 300^\circ\text{C}}{510^\circ\text{C} - 300^\circ\text{C}} & 300^\circ\text{C} \leq T \leq 510^\circ\text{C} \\ 1 & T > 510^\circ\text{C} \end{cases}$$

Results and Discussions

Morphology of CNTS on carbon fiber at low temperature

$D \approx 14-16 \text{ nm}$

Data of RAMAN & TGA

Raman spectra analysis and thermogravimetric analysis

Functional properties

- Increases the number of electrical percolation pathways within the uppermost ply, improving electron transportation
- Forms electrical percolation pathways within the interlaminar regions
- Bridges the insulating interlaminar regions

- Enhances phonon coupling
- Reduces scattering from the interlaminar regions dominated by the thermally insulating polymer matrix

Numerical Results

Numerical damage area in the CFRP composites

20 kA

40 kA

1st Layer

Numerical Results

Numerical damage area in the CFRP composites

1st Layer

2nd Layer

3rd Layer

4th Layer

Numerical Results

Electrical potential and Temperature profile in the thickness direction at 40 μs

Numerical Results

Damage area prediction

Fuzzy fiber (FF) composites

0.1G/FF composites

Conclusion

Modified carbon fiber composites with CNTs and GNPs

Functional conductivity

- Improving electron transfer conductive pathways
- Efficient heat transfer pathway across the laminate

Mechanical conductivity

- Increasing mechanical interlocking
- Improving fillers-matrix interfacial interaction
- Better stress transfer
- Reducing delamination issue

Numerical Model

- Predicting damage of CFRP with and without an LSP system
 - Damage of shape, area, and depth